

**Meise
Botanic Garden**

Science Strategy

**Meise Botanic Garden,
2026 - 2035**

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Executive summary

Plant diversity is under growing threat due to habitat loss from changing land use, overexploitation, pollution, the spread of invasive species, and climate change. These alarming changes in biodiversity and ecosystem health present significant societal challenges. Meise Botanic Garden's *Science Strategy 2026–2035* outlines our commitment to addressing these challenges through innovative scientific research leveraging our invaluable collections and by raising public awareness about the critical importance of plant diversity.

To address the societal challenges of the 21st century and demonstrate how our scientific research contributes to overcoming them, we have defined ten research ambitions for the period 2026–2035. The first five ambitions focus on *what we will investigate* and they are each aligned with a specific societal challenge.

- 1. Safeguarding the Belgian flora:** maintaining our leading role as an expertise centre for the documentation and conservation of the Belgian flora.
- 2. Contributing to global conservation challenges:** monitoring and conserving threatened species and vulnerable ecosystems globally, and in tropical Africa and Europe in particular.
- 3. Taking on global change challenges for plant diversity:** contributing to addressing global environmental challenges by documenting and studying the factors most prominently threatening plant diversity.
- 4. Understanding and recording biodiversity:** expanding our leadership in taxonomic research, to ensure that the foundational knowledge of biodiversity continues to underpin global conservation and sustainable development efforts.
- 5. Contributing to food and health security through conserving crop genetic resources:** Applying our expertise in conservation and valorisation of crops such as coffee, bananas, beans and edible mushrooms and of Belgian crop genetic resources.

Within each research ambition, we have identified different priorities and set clear goals to be achieved over the next decade. Complementing these thematic ambitions are five overarching ambitions that outline *how we will conduct our research, emphasising our commitment to fostering a dynamic scientific ecosystem.*

- 6. Focusing on (inter)national collaboration and capacity building:** consolidating Meise Botanic Garden as a leading European institute for innovative research on plants, fungi, and algae through collaboration and training
- 7. Doing science in state-of-the-art research infrastructure:** undertaking an ambitious renovation of our collection- and research building, transforming it into a state-of-the-art research campus.
- 8. Providing expert services:** expanding our expert services while looking for new market opportunities and optimising customer satisfaction.
- 9. Embracing open science and open data:** making our findings widely available to researchers, policy-makers, and the public, by embracing open access platforms, using interoperable data repositories, and engaging in global partnerships.
- 10. Bringing science to the public:** engaging the public in understanding plant diversity via public oriented events, publishing scientific papers and developing online platforms.

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Vision for science

Plants, fungi, and algae are vital components of ecosystems, providing essential goods and services that sustain life. They play a critical role in ecosystem functioning, such as soil formation and regulating carbon levels in the atmosphere. These organisms also provide food, livestock feed, pharmaceuticals, sustainable building materials, textiles, and energy. Additionally, they purify water and air, and they are increasingly important in mitigating climate change through carbon storage. Beyond their practical benefits, plants, fungi, and algae offer a source of enjoyment, relaxation, and learning, and they define local identities.

However, their diversity is under growing threat due to habitat loss from changing land use, overexploitation, pollution, the spread of invasive species, and climate change. These alarming changes in biodiversity and ecosystem health present significant societal challenges. The Meise Botanic Garden *Science Strategy* outlines our commitment to addressing these challenges through innovative scientific research leveraging our invaluable collections and by raising public awareness about the critical importance of plant diversity.

This *Science Strategy* works in conjunction with the *Science Collections*, *Living Collections*, and *Public Outreach Strategies* to achieve the overarching mission of Meise Botanic Garden: “*Building a sustainable future through discovery, research, and conservation of plants.*”

Our vision for science

At Meise Botanic Garden, we strive to consolidate ourselves as a leading European institute for innovative research on plants, fungi, and algae. In addition to valorising our work through high-impact scientific publications, we aim to evolve towards performing society- and policy-oriented research. Our work includes both fundamental and applied research, integrating cutting-edge technologies such as big data analytics, AI, and modern identification techniques with traditional expertise in taxonomy and comparative morphology.

By leveraging strategic partnerships with external collaborators, we seek to broaden our impact across research domains such as taxonomy and systematics, the study of wild relatives of food crops, and plant conservation. We distinguish ourselves by performing collection-based research on plants, fungi, and algae to address pressing societal challenges.

Collaboration and knowledge sharing are the cornerstones of our approach. Within our research community, interdisciplinary teamwork fosters synergies, where the exchange of ideas and experiences fuels innovation. We actively engage with the national and international research community and are committed to translating scientific insights into accessible knowledge and inspiring public interest in biodiversity. Furthermore, we are dedicated to training the next generation of researchers, ensuring a sustainable future for plant science.

Science at Meise Botanic Garden

Meise Botanic Garden is a Flemish scientific institute operating within the policy domain for Work, Economy, Science, Innovation, Agriculture, and Social Economy. The 2024–2029 policy note on Economy, Science, Innovation, and Industry by Minister-President Diependaele emphasises the pivotal role of Meise Botanic Garden:

“Meise Botanic Garden is a leading knowledge center for plant diversity. With 20,000 living plant species and 4 million preserved specimens, it ranks among the largest botanical gardens in the world. Scientists there study plant diversity, evolution, ecology, and the conservation of vascular plants, algae, fungi, and lichens from diverse regions such as Europe, Central Africa, and Antarctica. In 2009, a master plan was developed to enhance Meise Botanic Garden. This plan continues to be implemented.”

The investments in Meise Botanic Garden are part of a broader Flemish government initiative to invest in a strong knowledge base, in which state-of-the-art research infrastructure plays a crucial role. The planned research activities of Meise Botanic Garden align well with the objectives of this policy, advancing fundamental knowledge of plants, which in turn benefits other applied research that addresses pressing societal challenges, from biodiversity conservation to food security. This research is achieved through enhanced collaboration with Flemish universities through the FWO-Meise Botanic Garden fellowships and targeted project applications at various levels: international, European (Horizon Europe, European Development and Cooperation, LIFE, COST Actions, European Research Infrastructures), national (BRAIN-be), Walloon (FNRS, ARES), and Flemish (FWO). We also benefit from partnerships with private foundations such as the Franklinia Foundation, the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, and the King Baudouin Foundation. Through both formal and informal education about various aspects of botany, ranging from biodiversity to biotechnology, we spark interest in science and technology among young people, contributing to STEM objectives. Our citizen science projects further cultivate public engagement and societal support for scientific research. Finally, by providing research data to the FRIS Research Portal and expanding access to our collections, we actively support open data and open access initiatives, in line with the European Open Science Cloud initiative by the European Commission and the Flemish Open Science policy spearheaded by the Flemish Open Science Board.

To address the societal challenges of the 21st century and demonstrate how our scientific research contributes to overcoming them, we have defined ten research ambitions for the period 2026–2035. The first five ambitions focus on *what* we will investigate and they are each aligned with a specific societal challenge. Within each research ambition, we have identified a number of priorities and set clear goals to be achieved over the next decade. These research ambitions will be led by dedicated teams of scientists, collaborating closely with both internal and external partners. Complementing these thematic ambitions are five overarching ambitions that outline how we will conduct our research, emphasising our commitment to fostering a dynamic scientific ecosystem. To achieve these ambitions, we highlight the importance of promoting diversity among our scientists across all dimensions, including gender, origin, and age, and adhering to the principles of open science and scientific integrity, as outlined in our integrity, HR, and gender equality plans.

Research ambitions

Ambition 1

Safeguarding the Belgian flora

Over the past centuries, the Belgian flora has become strongly impoverished due to urbanisation, intensification of agriculture, pollution, invasive species, and overexploitation. On top of all this, a rapidly changing climate places additional stress on population survival in our highly fragmented landscapes. The remaining flora is in a precarious state, requiring careful monitoring and restoration to prevent further species loss. The decline in biodiversity also jeopardises essential ecosystem services and functions and a healthy living environment.

In Belgium, different stakeholders are involved in safeguarding and studying our flora and fauna. To maximise research and conservation efforts and to fulfill international commitments, a strong network among these actors is essential. Meise Botanic Garden is committed to maintaining its leading role as an expertise centre for the documentation and conservation of the Belgian flora. Through scientific collaborations, publications such as *Dumortiera* and the *Flora of Belgium*, network events, and through partnerships with societies such as the Royal Botanical Society of Belgium, we aim to unite national and European stakeholders and advance the protection of our botanical heritage.

Priority 1.1

Assessing biodiversity and ecosystem health *in situ*

Given the ongoing human impact on nature in Belgium, continuous monitoring of biodiversity in the field remains crucial for collecting the necessary data to inform nature management decisions. Regular field surveys across the Belgian territory in combination with detailed long-term monitoring at designated sites, such as the LTER (Long Term Ecological Research) sites, is essential for tracking the effects of non-native species, for quantifying species turnover due to climate change or eutrophication, and for assessing the viability of populations of red listed species or species listed under the European Habitat Directive. We aim to take a leading role in *in situ* monitoring of plants, fungi, and algae in Belgium while building the necessary capacity to provide expert support to partner institutes and organisations involved in plant diversity monitoring. In addition, in-depth monitoring of changes in the genetic integrity of the native Belgian flora is necessary, as subtle changes in population viability may otherwise go unnoticed. Such genetic monitoring requires the development of innovative techniques and the availability of expertise for data analyses and interpretation. Finally, we will actively facilitate collaboration among actors (e.g. INBO, Natuurpunt, and Natagora) involved in monitoring the Belgian flora (including mosses, lichens, fungi, and diatoms) to establish coherent monitoring strategies and to deliver actionable policy recommendations and up-to-date red-lists for the Belgian flora.

Priority 1.2 Mitigating nutrient enrichment effects

Flanders faces high levels of nitrogen deposition, primarily from emissions related to traffic, agriculture, and industrial activities. The negative impacts of nitrogen deposition on biodiversity are well-established and widely recognised. However, the relative contribution of nitrogen deposition compared to other drivers negatively affecting species conservation objectives and habitats remains insufficiently studied. Investigating these other drivers and their relationship to nitrogen deposition can lead to alternative strategies for achieving conservation objectives. In addition to direct nitrogen impacts, Flemish ecosystems are under strong pressure from factors such as (i) desiccation, which causes nitrogen to mineralise from organic soils, preventing excess nutrients from being flushed out by seepage water; (ii) inadequate management practices, driven by large-scale mechanisation in nature management, and (iii) habitat fragmentation, resulting in inbreeding and genetic impoverishment. These factors can exacerbate the negative effects of nitrogen deposition, sometimes making it difficult to clearly determine its contribution to biodiversity decline, especially in relation to changes in the stoichiometry of nitrogen relative to other elements. To strengthen nitrogen impact research in Flanders, we plan to establish a nitrogen research unit in collaboration with other Flemish research institutes. Meise Botanic Garden will leverage its current extensive expertise in monitoring plant diversity, nature conservation and restoration, and population genetics to contribute to a deeper understanding of nitrogen deposition and help mitigate its effects on the environment.

Priority 1.3 Restoring plant communities

Due to urbanisation and the intensification of agriculture over the past centuries, nature in Belgium has been severely degraded, with areas of high conservation value becoming increasingly fragmented and isolated. In this context, active nature restoration is essential to ensure that Belgium meets its international commitments to biodiversity conservation in the short term. Meise Botanic Garden will continue collaborating with nature conservation organisations, academic institutions, and other governmental research institutes to address the challenge of conserving nature in the highly anthropogenic Belgian landscape. Given our expertise in *ex situ* conservation, plant ecology, and plant population genetics, Meise Botanic Garden can play a pivotal role in providing scientific support to plant community restoration efforts while aligning nature conservation with the demands for a profitable agriculture and an increased urbanisation. In the coming decade, we aim to strengthen our expertise in: (i) the use of local seed mixtures for restoration of plant communities in natural and semi-natural habitats, (ii) the translocation of plant and fungal communities, (iii) the development of climate-adapted plant communities, and (iv) innovative solutions for urban greening, contributing to the creation of healthy urban environments.

Priority 1.4 Reinforcing and reintroducing populations of threatened species

In densely populated regions like Flanders, many plant species have small and fragmented populations, with rare and threatened species particularly at risk of extinction despite habitat restoration efforts. One technique to halt the loss of such species is conservation translocation, which involves intentionally relocating populations for conservation purposes. Over the past decade, Meise Botanic Garden has developed extensive expertise in the reintroduction and reinforcement of degraded populations of rare and threatened species, usually as part of larger EU-funded LIFE projects. However, to ensure the long-term success of plant reintroduction and population reinforcements, multidisciplinary research is necessary. This research helps identify and address the underlying causes of population decline, enabling well-informed decisions at different stages of the process. Therefore, we plan to further invest in: (i) population genetic research to detect harmful genetic changes, (ii) optimisation of seed germination and plant cultivation protocols to maximise establishment success, (iii) *in situ* and population genetic monitoring to quantify success rates, and (iv) assessing climate adaptation of rare species, which represents an important knowledge gap. Through these efforts, we aim to consolidate Meise Botanic Garden as a centre of expertise in science-based plant reintroductions, population reinforcements, and de-extinction efforts.

Priority 1.5 Optimising *ex situ* conservation methods

While *in situ* conservation remains the preferred method for plant conservation, *ex situ* conservation of plants outside their natural habitats serves as an important backup to prevent the loss of populations and even species extinction. Depending on the ecological characteristics of species and their seed storage behaviour, different *ex situ* conservation methods can be considered. For species with drought-tolerant seeds, seed banking is considered the most resource-efficient method, as it allows the storage of a large amount of genetic diversity with little effort. For species that only reproduce clonally or that have non drought-tolerant seeds, alternative methods such as *ex situ* collections within our domain or glasshouses, cryo-preservation, or *in vitro* conservation should be considered. Given the urgency of conserving what remains of our natural biodiversity, efforts have primarily focused on collecting and preserving what is left of our native flora. While continued collecting efforts will remain a high priority in the coming decade, we will also focus on studying: (i) the effects of *ex situ* conservation on seed and plant viability, and strategies to minimise viability loss; (ii) the optimisation of conservation practices to reduce effects of artificial selection and genetic erosion, (iii) cryopreservation and *in vitro* conservation techniques for conserving species with recalcitrant seeds or dust seeds and exclusively clonal species. Meise Botanic Garden is committed to further developing its expertise in *ex situ* conservation practices, positioning itself as a global leader in this field.

Ambition 2 **Contributing to global conservation challenges**

Global biodiversity conservation faces numerous challenges, driven by a combination of human activities and environmental changes. Habitat destruction due to agriculture, deforestation, and urbanisation remains a primary threat that fragments ecosystems and reduces the space available for plant species to thrive. Climate change exacerbates these pressures by altering temperature and precipitation patterns, disrupting the balance many plants require to survive. Overharvesting of plants for food, medicine, and ornamental purposes also places significant strain on many species, particularly those already vulnerable. To address these issues, global cooperation, innovative conservation strategies, and increased education and training about the importance of plants to ecosystems and human well-being are essential. Building on decades of experience in plant conservation and its expert knowledge of plants, fungi, and algae, Meise Botanic Garden will take up its responsibility to monitor and conserve threatened species and vulnerable ecosystems globally, and in tropical Africa and Europe in particular.

Priority 2.1 ***In situ* monitoring and conservation status assessments**

The first key step in plant conservation is to compile adequate knowledge of the current plant species distributions, their correct identities, and population viability. In addition, understanding species ecology and their interactions with other species, such as pollinators and fungi, is needed to assess ecosystem functioning, health, and resilience in the context of global change. While temperate ecosystems are fairly well explored, large knowledge gaps exist for (sub)tropical ecosystems, particularly in Africa. Our science collections, which are the results of decades of field work and explorations, form the basis for our taxonomic research but they also contain a wealth of data on species identity, occurrences, and ecology, as outlined in our *Science Collection Strategy*. This information is invaluable for making IUCN conservation status assessments, modelling current and future plant distributions, making checklists, and monitoring water quality via surveying communities of microscopic algae. We aim to strengthen our plant, fungi, and algae monitoring efforts globally, and particularly in tropical Africa, by assisting local institutions in performing field expeditions and setting up monitoring networks. We will continue our active involvement in IUCN red-listing assessments of tropical taxa. Furthermore, Meise Botanic Garden will participate in large-scale biodiversity monitoring projects, such as the Green Heart of Africa initiative, to inventory and explore current biodiversity and to train local biodiversity researchers. Finally, we will invest in the development of local infrastructure for collection and data management at selected sites, alongside capacity-building initiatives for both academic and non-academic partners.

Priority 2.2 Conserving threatened exceptional species and species extinct in the wild

About 45% of flowering plant species are at risk of extinction. Habitat loss from expansion of agricultural land, logging, and urbanisation necessitates targeted *in situ* conservation actions to prevent the total disappearance of species from their natural habitats. For species that are extinct in the wild or nearing extinction, *ex situ* conservation is the last resort. In this context, further research is needed to analyse the effects of genetic bottlenecks or potential maladaptation to natural environments due to genetic drift or artificial selection. This is particularly important for tropical species and tree species, which often produce recalcitrant seeds, making it challenging to store large amounts of genetic diversity in seed banks or field gene banks. Meise Botanic Garden will contribute to the global safeguarding of threatened species by implementing a metacollection approach, under the guidance of Botanic Gardens Conservation International, which will monitor and connect populations of threatened species in botanic gardens and in the wild, as outlined in the *Living Collections Strategy*. By leveraging our expertise in taxonomy and molecular genetics, we will study the genetic diversity and structure of threatened species in both *ex situ* collections and remaining *in situ* populations. The goal is to optimise decision-making regarding the exchange of plant material, cultivation practices, and *in situ* conservation. We will work closely with scientists from other botanic gardens around the world, as well as local scientists, to develop robust conservation, reintroduction, and population reinforcement protocols aimed at preventing species extinction.

Priority 2.3 Reforestation and promoting sustainable agroforestry

Reconciling nature restoration with sustainable development requires balancing ecological integrity with pressing social and economic needs. Effective strategies should integrate biodiversity conservation into livelihoods, ensuring that restoration efforts enhance food security, reduce poverty, and support resilient communities. Science-based conservation decisions and nature-based solutions can contribute significantly to reconcile societal needs. For example, appropriate management of community forests and other habitats outside protected areas not only contributes to biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation, but also to improving local livelihoods. In the framework of the commitment of Flanders to contribute to international climate actions, coordinated by the Departement Omgeving of the Flemish government, Meise Botanic Garden has already successfully managed reforestation projects. These range from large-scale reforestation projects to establishing agroforestry systems of coffee in the Democratic Republic of the Congo. These efforts occur in collaboration with international research institutes, such as CIFOR-ICRAF, governmental agencies, and local communities. The challenges in this field remain substantial, and we aim to play an important role by providing scientific expertise and practical experience in the evaluation and use of local genetic resources, and the establishment of nurseries and training. Meise Botanic Garden aims to (i) further develop and apply its expertise in the fields of reforestation, agroforestry, and sustainable development in tropical Africa, (ii) collaborate with international and local actors to ensure community-supported project implementation, such as the green corridor initiative in the Democratic Republic of the Congo, and (iii) provide policy recommendations for sustainable development.

Ambition 3 **Taking on global change challenges for plant diversity**

The world is facing a range of biodiversity challenges driven by human population growth and associated activities. The conversion of natural habitats into farmland is currently the leading cause of biodiversity loss worldwide. In the Global North, the excessive use of fertilisers leads to water and soil pollution, which in turn negatively affects species diversity in both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. Europe, as a hub for trade and travel, is particularly vulnerable to invasive species that outcompete native biota, disrupt ecosystems, and introduce diseases. As an international trade hub, Belgium also plays an important role in combatting illegal logging and illegal trade in plants and animals. Additionally, the impact of climate change, rising temperatures, shifting weather patterns, more frequent and severe heat waves, droughts, and floods, pose significant risks to species survival and migration. Meise Botanic Garden will contribute to addressing these environmental challenges by documenting and studying the factors most prominently threatening global plant diversity.

Priority 3.1 **Data-based monitoring of biodiversity change**

Understanding and addressing biodiversity change is critical to achieve national, European, and global conservation goals, including the Belgian National Biodiversity Strategy, the European Biodiversity Strategy, and the Global Biodiversity Framework. As data on biodiversity continues to grow, driven by advances in digitisation and the mobilisation of specimen and observational data, their effective use depends on standardisation, accessibility, and integration into decision-making processes. At Meise Botanic Garden, we are at the forefront of efforts to mobilise and standardise botanical data, ensuring they adhere to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. By linking diverse data sources and fostering interoperability, we provide the foundation for robust, repeatable workflows that support informed policy and management actions. Our work embraces cutting-edge technologies, such as environmental DNA (eDNA), automated image analysis, and integrated virtual research environments, enabling new insights into biodiversity trends. By pairing these tools with citizen science initiatives, we empower communities to contribute to biodiversity monitoring and management, fostering broader engagement in conservation effort. Botanical taxonomy and nomenclature remain at the heart of our mission, underpinning the accurate identification and classification of plants and fungi, a cornerstone for understanding and mitigating biodiversity change. Through our leadership in biodiversity informatics, we aim to (i) bridge critical knowledge gaps, (ii) enhance collaborative research, and (iii) provide actionable insights for ecosystem restoration and sustainable management. By integrating technology, data mobilisation, and community engagement, we contribute to the transformation of biodiversity monitoring and management, supporting evidence-based conservation decisions across Europe and beyond.

Priority 3.2 Climate change impact assessments

Significant climate change, including rising temperatures and altered precipitation patterns, has already profoundly impacted biodiversity in recent decades. These changes have driven shifts in species phenology, distribution, and community composition. While the direct contribution of climate change to species extinctions has so far been limited, its impact is projected to increase, with up to 30% of European plant species at risk of extinction by 2080. Understanding and predicting the potential impact of global climate change on individual species and plant communities is crucial for guiding policymakers and designing climate-resilient conservation strategies and food systems. The science collections and archives at Meise Botanic Garden serve as invaluable sources of information for reconstructing the effects of climate change over the past century and informing models predicting future trends. Meise Botanic Garden aims to (i) leverage its collections by extracting data from herbarium specimens, living collections, and archives to study changes in plant traits and phenological events, (ii) develop and apply predictive models, such as species distribution models, to forecast climate-driven shifts in plant distributions, and (iii) conduct experimental research by reciprocal transplant and greenhouse experiments for specific plant species to investigate adaptive responses and resilience to climate change. Efforts will focus on translating scientific findings into actionable policy briefs and contributing to international discussions addressing climate change risks.

Priority 3.3 Deforestation and commodity tracing

Deforestation and forest degradation are driven in significant ways by local and international demand for timber and agricultural commodities and the profits made from export markets. The effectiveness of legal initiatives designed to reduce demand by restricting market access for timber or crops grown on inappropriately deforested land hinges on traceability and tools that allow civil society actors and enforcement agencies to objectively scrutinise location of harvest claims. The implementation of the new EU deforestation regulation will demand new techniques that can aid in achieving the imposed commitments. Meise Botanic Garden will focus on the development of innovative scientific techniques that allow the determination or verification of the harvest location of timber or agricultural crops, with a special focus on coffee and cacao. Specifically, we will develop and optimise chemical (stable isotope ratios and trace elements) and genetic methods, combined with state-of-the-art geospatial models that allow large-scale and high-resolution predictions of harvest location. To this end, we will optimise laboratory protocols for the chemical fingerprinting and downstream database building and data analysis. Additionally, we will leverage satellite, land cover, species distribution, climate and soil datasets to empower these models further and to allow prediction in areas where reference samples are unavailable. As a consortium partner to the World Forest ID initiative, Meise Botanic Garden is the collection facility for a section of the World Forest ID reference collection (especially for timber, soy, coffee, and cocoa). Future research areas that will be explored include forensic soil analysis, nutrient analysis for agricultural soils, and correlating crop elemental uptake with nutritional values.

Ambition 4

Understanding and recording biodiversity

The science collections of Meise Botanic Garden represent a remarkable and irreplaceable source of information about organisms and the world they inhabit. In Belgium, we hold the leading position in studying the diversity of a wide range of organisms such as plants, fungi, algae, and myxomycetes and we use this expertise to tackle the numerous biodiversity challenges of our time. A profound understanding of contemporary biological diversity and how it arose is key if we want to conserve and exploit this diversity. Discovering, describing, naming, and classifying species has been one of the core tasks of Meise Botanic Garden for decades. As academic institutions increasingly shift focus away from traditional taxonomic and morphological research, the role of research institutes such as botanic gardens and natural history museums becomes ever more critical in preserving and advancing this field. By maintaining and expanding our leadership in taxonomic research, we aim to ensure that the foundational knowledge of biodiversity continues to underpin global conservation and sustainable development efforts.

Priority 4.1

Documenting the world's flora through naming, describing, revising, and classifying

An understanding of what species are and how to identify them is essential to grasp the diversity of the living world. Hundreds of thousands of plant species exist on Earth, but many species have yet to be discovered while only minimal information is known about others. It is only by understanding, revising, and naming species that we can shape the social, political, and financial forces that affect conservation efforts and sustainable use. Naming, revising, and classifying species, often referred to as taxonomic research, has been at the core of our scientific activities for over a century. Initially based on morphological and anatomical comparisons, the fast development of chemical and especially genetic tools has revolutionised the revision of species. Integrative and accelerated taxonomy emphasises the combined use of different tools for species revisions and taxonomy, an approach that is also embraced by our scientists. While fundamental taxonomic research suffers from a decreased interest and limited opportunities for funding, Meise Botanic Garden remains committed to maintaining taxonomy at the core of its research activities. Moreover, we aim to (i) consolidate our expertise in taxonomic research on plants, fungi, algae, and myxomycetes with a focus on Europe and tropical Africa, (ii) invest in training the next generation of taxonomists and field biologists, (iii) unlock knowledge through printed and online floras and scientific manuscripts, and (iv) contribute to global flora initiatives, such as World Flora Online and AlgaeBase. Our taxonomic expertise will be valorised by providing identification services and by contributing to conservation efforts via improved red listing and identification of regions of high diversity via existing modeling tools.

Priority 4.2 Building and refining the tree-of-life

The rapid advancements in molecular genetics and bio-informatics have revolutionised our ability to reconstruct the tree-of-life, to reveal how species are related to each other, and to test hypotheses about the evolution of life on Earth. These tools also enable the identification of unknown organisms or the detection of taxa not visible to the naked eye. Over the past decade, Meise Botanic Garden has continuously invested in improving its molecular lab infrastructure and in attracting expert scientists. This has resulted in a significant increase in the use of molecular genetic tools to classify species and to make appropriate decisions for conservation practices. In the coming decade, through its expertise and collections, Meise Botanic Garden commits to join international initiatives on reconstructing the tree of life, such as Biodiversity Genomics Europe, PAFTOL, Darwin NGT, and the Global Genome Biodiversity Network. These contributions will be realised by the strategic use and unlocking of our extensive herbarium and living collections, as well as by staying on top of developments in the fields of molecular phylogenetics and genomics. We aim to play a central role in the reconstruction of the tree of life for taxa for which we have world class expertise, such as Combretaceae, Malvaceae, Poaceae, and Rubiaceae, as well as mosses, marine algae, lichens, and fungi. In addition, given our extensive scientific collections from tropical Africa and our longstanding expertise and international research network, we are uniquely positioned to be the leading contributor to the tree of life for this region. Through high-impact publications and contributions to conservation practices, we will ensure that our findings not only advance scientific understanding but also translate into tangible benefits for biodiversity preservation.

Priority 4.3 Understanding evolution

Based on our extensive collections and using the latest techniques, our scientists answer fundamental questions about the origins of biodiversity, such as: 'What are species?' 'How does diversity arise?' and 'How can we explain that biodiversity varies in time and space?' We perform both micro- and macro-evolutionary research to study past and ongoing evolutionary processes. We study co-evolution and the evolution of species interactions, such as the association between fungi and algae in lichens, leaf and root endophytes, and vascular plants with microbial and fungal symbionts, e.g. mycorrhiza. With a wealth of collection data increasing accessibility through digitisation, combined with our scientists' complementary expertise in morphology, molecular biology, and modeling, Meise Botanic Garden is uniquely equipped to take a leading position in evolutionary research. We aim to deepen our understanding of evolutionary processes by (i) staying at the forefront of evolutionary modeling, with complex models to predict diversification, trait evolution, and biogeography, (ii) integrating expertise across disciplines, morphology, ecology, and molecular biology, to explore innovative areas of biodiversity evolution, (iii) studying species interactions, such as mutualism, commensalism, and parasitism, and (iv) conducting experiments to study speciation processes and barriers for hybridisation. This research will be published in high-impact journals and will provide us a deeper understanding of the living world.

Priority 4.4
Linking traits to evolution through comparative morphology and anatomy

A profound knowledge of morphology is needed to correctly classify organisms, but it is also essential to understand the function of structures and how organisms are adapted to their environment. The main aim of comparative morphology is to compare the form of organisms or their parts to understand their evolution. Trait data are becoming increasingly available in online repositories and are often used in eco-evolutionary studies and to feed models that aim to predict effects of global change on ecosystems, such as functional diversity metrics. A thorough understanding of morphology and how it evolved, is however crucially important to correctly interpret such models. Our scientists master the skill of studying morphology and anatomy of a wide range of organisms, such as unicellular algae, lichens, fungi, and vascular plants. They use advanced preparation and imaging techniques such as light microscopy, digital microscopes, and scanning electron microscopy to expose and compare morphological features that are not visible to the naked eye. The different morphological features are visualised by means of photographs and botanical drawings, which allow to emphasise certain structural features. Given the value of this meticulous and important work to understand the living world, we intend to solidify our position as expertise centre for morphological and anatomical studies by: (i) investing in state-of-the-art imaging and preparation techniques, (ii) training the next generation of plant morphologists, (iii) applying this knowledge to better inform models for reconstructing plant evolution and predicting global change effects, and (iv) valorising the collections for future research by linking morphological information to specimens.

Ambition 5
Contributing to food and health security through conserving crop genetic resources

Genetic resources are essential for ensuring global food security, as they provide the foundation for developing resilient, high-yielding, and climate-adapted crops. Preserving the genetic diversity of plants allows breeders to enhance resistance to pests, diseases, and environmental stressors, ensuring stable food production in the face of global challenges like climate change. By maintaining a diverse gene pool, we can safeguard the long-term sustainability and adaptability of agricultural systems, securing nutritious food for growing populations. Crop wild relatives (CWRs) hold promise in meeting these needs, as they demonstrate resilience to a range of environmental and biological stresses and possess valuable genetic diversity for crossing and breeding. Meise Botanic Garden has already developed expertise in conservation and valorisation of crops such as coffee, bananas, beans, and edible mushrooms. This expertise will be applied to conserve other tropical genetic resources such as Vanilla and temperate species such as carrots and chicory.

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Priority 5.1 Optimising conservation and use of wild *Musa* genetic resources

Bananas, the most consumed fruit worldwide, are an essential source of nutrition and income for local communities in the tropics. However, their overall genetic diversity is very limited due to their clonal propagation, a result of the lack of seeds in the fruit. In contrast, the wild relatives of edible bananas display a particularly rich genetic variation. Yet, wild bananas are currently significantly underrepresented in global collections. This lack of interest in wild bananas strongly contrasts with their tremendous potential as a the basis for new climate- and disease resilient banana cultivars. The wild relatives of edible bananas are a valuable source of alleles that provide drought tolerance or disease resistance, thereby playing a fundamental role in safeguarding future banana cultivation in a changing climate. Modern genotyping and phenotyping technologies enable us to identify and harness the genetic potential of wild banana species, paving the way for optimised banana cultivation. In 2024, Meise Botanic Garden, together with the Alliance of Bioversity International and the International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT), launched the World Banana Seed Bank. The mission of the World Banana Seed Bank is to conserve wild banana genetic diversity by storing seeds from various species and populations. While baseline research has been conducted on the collection and storage of seeds, significant challenges still need to be addressed to improve the regeneration and conservation of wild bananas in *ex situ* conditions. Therefore, we will focus on (i) determining optimal storage conditions for pollen and seeds, (ii) optimising growing conditions and hand-pollination practices in the glasshouse, and (iii) discovering wild diversity conservation gaps using molecular genetic techniques. In the coming decade, we aim to create a fully operational banana seed and pollen bank, safeguarding wild *Musa* genetic resources for stakeholders like smallholders, scientists, and breeders. Our expertise will be shared to establish local *Musa* seed banks in Southeast Asia, the region of origin of wild *Musa*. This approach will improve *Musa* biodiversity and support future banana cultivation by providing valuable genetic resources for breeding and research.

Priority 5.2 Contributing to the protein shift with bean genetic resources

Grain legumes, including beans, are rich in proteins (16–50%), essential elements, dietary fibre, and vitamins. Legumes are also adapted to a wide range of environmental conditions, growing both in temperate and tropical climates. In addition, the capacity for biological nitrogen fixation, deep root systems, low input requirements, and the ability to grow and survive in nutrient poor, dry, and saline soils make grain legumes a popular alternative for the farming community in the current cereal dominated cropping systems. It is widely anticipated that grain legumes are a crucial component in shifting towards a more sustainable diet. Although the importance of grain legumes in low-income countries is widely known, a shift from animal-based towards vegetable-based proteins is also high on the European agenda for the coming decade as expressed in the Green Deal Protein shift. Since the late 1980s, we have curated one of the most diverse collections of Phaseoleae, encompassing the economically important *Phaseolus* and *Vigna* beans. After a decreased interest in research on Phaseoleae over the past decade, we aim to establish ourselves again as an excellence centre for research and knowledge on wild and cultivated Phaseoleae beans. Future research activities will focus on (i) studying taxonomy and evolution of wild and cultivated Phaseoleae, including the detection of conservation gaps, (ii) phenotypical and genotypical characterisation of Phaseoleae with an emphasis on climate adaptation, and (iii) capacity building on the conservation and use of legumes.

Priority 5.3 Exploring coffee genetic resources to improve local livelihoods

About 99% of the world's coffee production is based on two species, *Coffea arabica* ('Arabica coffee') and *C. canephora* ('Robusta coffee'). Drought, extreme temperatures, and heavy rains due to climate change continue to adversely affect both yield and cup quality leading to a shortage of high-quality Arabica coffee in world markets. Robusta's natural resistance to diseases and pests, adaptation to warmer climates, and higher productivity therefore highlight its significance for the future of coffee production. While Robusta shows promise in addressing market challenges due to its genetic diversity, barriers such as improving flavour profiles, farmer profitability, and climate adaptation persist. Breeding efforts are hindered by limited access to agronomic and genetic resources. It is now widely recognised that the key to sustaining coffee as an affordable crop lies in the genetic variation found in coffee germplasm collections. Over the past decade, Meise Botanic Garden, in collaboration with local and international partners, has developed the Yangambi INERA and CNRS Lwiro coffee collections into two of the most important genetic resource collections for central African *Coffea* species. Building on this foundation, we aim to establish our institute as the leading knowledge institute for coffee in the Democratic Republic of the Congo and to create a central African coffee consortium and training centre in partnership with international and local stakeholders. We aim to (i) consolidate the coffee collections of Lwiro and Yangambi as fully operational hubs capable of providing access to coffee genetic resources for cultivation, (ii) advance research into climate adaptation and disease resistance, and continue the description and inventory of wild *Coffea* genetic diversity, (iii) bridge the knowledge gap from plants to roasted coffee by providing training at all levels, which should lead to local coffee production as a reliable source of income for local farmers and reducing the pressure on the tropical rainforest.

Priority 5.4 Documenting wild edible mushrooms in tropical Africa and promoting their cultivation

Mushrooms can play a vital role in providing food security in tropical regions, where they are not only an important food source but also valued for their medicinal properties. The practice of collecting edible mushrooms has been passed down from generation to generation and many communities, particularly women, have long traditions in picking mushrooms, contributing both to their nutrition and to the empowerment of women. However, there remains a significant gap in knowledge about edible mushroom species and their inventory and documentation is critical for preserving and sharing the collective traditional knowledge. Meise Botanic Garden has developed invaluable expertise in mushroom identification, ethnomycology, and *ex situ* production of mushrooms in West and Central Africa. We will build on this expertise to establish a centre of expertise and training for the valorisation of wild edible mushrooms in South Kivu. This initiative aligns with our broader goal of advancing mycological research across tropical Africa, including Benin, Gabon, Democratic Republic of the Congo, and Rwanda. We will focus on (i) inventorying the diversity of edible mushrooms and sharing the data in the African species database, (ii) identifying key species with significant nutritional and economic value, (iii) developing low-cost cultivation techniques using residues from local agriculture, and (iv) building local capacity by training community members in mycology and mushroom cultivation techniques, thus fostering local expertise and ensuring the long-term success of the initiative.

Priority 5.5 **Establishing a network to conserve crop (wild) genetic resources in Flanders**

In situ and *ex situ* conservation are essential and complementary approaches for safeguarding the genetic diversity of cultivated crop varieties. In Flanders, however, the landscape of gene banks for cultivated varieties and crop wild relatives is highly fragmented and poorly developed, and the Global Strategy for Plant Conservation Target 9 was therefore not achieved. This target mandates that “70 percent of the genetic diversity of crops, including their wild relatives and other socio-economically valuable plant species, is conserved, with respect for and preservation of associated indigenous and local knowledge.” The newly adopted Convention on Biological Diversity includes a complementary voluntary action for the period 2024–2030 to “Undertake *ex situ* and *in situ* conservation programmes for genetic diversity in wild and domesticated plant species and populations, including crops and their wild relatives and other socio-economically valuable plant species, considering the domestication gradient and the use of surrogates or proxies, ensuring that the genetic diversity within and among populations is effectively documented, managed and monitored, to maintain and restore genetic diversity and safeguard their adaptive potential, taking into account the relevant frameworks and plans of action developed under the Commission on Genetic Resources

for Food and Agriculture of the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations.” To meet this ambitious target, a coordinated approach is essential for Flanders. Meise Botanic Garden, in collaboration with its partners, will take a leading role in developing a network for the conservation of crop genetic resources in Flanders by (i) optimising the conservation of crop genetic resources in Flanders, (ii) identifying conservation gaps on the European continent, and (iii) valorising phenotypic and genotypic data of selected genetic resources. In addition, we will actively participate in European initiatives for the conservation of crop genetic resources, such as the European Cooperative Programme for Plant Genetic Resources and Grace-RI.

Ambition 6 **Focusing on (inter)national collaboration and capacity building**

Priority 6.1 **Remaining a unique and leading research institution in Belgium**

Meise Botanic Garden is one of six Flemish Scientific Institutes (VWIs) of the Flemish government, alongside the Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture Fisheries and Food (ILVO), Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO), Flanders Hydraulics, Flanders Heritage Agency, and the Royal Museum of Fine Arts Antwerp (KMSKA). These VWIs conduct both fundamental research and provide scientific support for policy decisions through applied research. Together, they play a crucial role in the preparation and evaluation of policies in agriculture, nature conservation, water-related infrastructure, art, and cultural heritage. In addition to collaborations within the VWI network, Meise Botanic Garden actively works with other Flemish research institutions, such as the Vlaamse Landmaatschappij (VLM), Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO), and Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ). At the national level, we maintain strong collaborative ties with universities and several federal scientific institutes, such as the Royal Meteorological Institute (RMI), the Royal Belgian Institute for Natural Sciences (RBINS), the Royal Museum for Central Africa (RMCA), and Sciensano. Meise Botanic Garden has also signed a collaboration agreement with the Belgian Development Cooperation, ENABEL, to provide expertise in sustainable development projects. Finally, we are deeply involved in numerous societies, such as the Royal Botanical Society of Belgium (RBSB), the Royal Academy of Overseas Sciences (RAOS), and the Belgian Association of Botanic Gardens and Arboreta (VBTA), and communities, such as the Belgian Plant Science Community (BPSC), floristische werkgroepen VZW (flower), Vlaamse Werkgroep Bryologie en Lichenologie, and the Studygroup European and Mediterranean Orchids (SEMO).

Priority 6.2 **Consolidating Meise Botanic Garden as a leading European institute for innovative research on plants, fungi, and algae**

Meise Botanic Garden is embedded within several international networks and organisations, strengthening its global role in botanical research and conservation. As one of the largest botanic gardens in the world, we are an active member of Botanic Garden Conservation International, which represents over 100 botanic gardens. In addition, we have research collaboration agreements with individual botanic gardens. As an important taxonomic research institute, we are a member of the Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities (CETAF) and participate in global taxonomic consortia, such as World Flora Online (WFO), Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), and Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG). In the framework of research on securing plant genetic resources, we have established official partnerships with the Alliance Bioversity International - CIAT for research on and conservation of *Musa* genetic resources, with CIFOR-ICRAF for the creation of a coffee value chain in the Democratic Republic of the Congo, and with World Forest ID for tracing illegal timber and forest risk commodities. Informal research collaborations exist with other facilities, such as WorldVeg and the Crop Trust. At the European level, Meise Botanic Garden is increasingly involved in existing and emerging European Research Infrastructures such as DiSSCO, ELTER, and Grace-RI, alongside networks such as the European Native Seed Conservation Network (ENSCONET) and the European Cooperative Programme for Plant Genetic Resources (ECPGR). Meise Botanic Garden is also represented in working group 5.16.00 (wood identification) of the International Union of Forest Research Organizations (IUFRO). Our growing number of international collaborations over the past decade underscores our commitment to remaining one of Europe's foremost institutes for botanical research.

Meise Botanic Garden actively supports the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), with a particular focus on the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. Its efforts include conserving plant biodiversity both *in situ* and *ex situ*, engaging in sustainable use initiatives, and promoting public awareness about biodiversity issues. We contributed to the CBD's Global Strategy for Plant Conservation 2010 (GSPC), which aims to expand knowledge of plant diversity and prevent its loss, and we have also played a role in the updated version adopted at COP16 in 2024. As part of the CBD, the Nagoya Protocol focuses on access to genetic resources and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from their utilisation. We support this by ensuring that plant science is performed in accordance with these Access and Benefit Sharing principles and adheres to the requirements of the Nagoya Protocol and related international and national legislations. Finally, Meise Botanic Garden increasingly contributes to several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including Goal 13 (Climate Action), Goal 15 (Life on Land), and Goal 4 (Quality Education).

Priority 6.3 Establishing a research centre and research network in tropical Africa

Since the late 19th and early 20th centuries, there has been a strong interest in the study of botanical diversity in tropical Africa, particularly within the former Belgian colonies of the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Rwanda, and Burundi. This research interest was closely tied to the discovery and exploitation of plant genetic resources, as exemplified by the activities of the National Institute for Agronomic Study of the Belgian Congo (INEAC) from 1933 to 1960. During this period, Meise Botanic Garden received large numbers of botanical specimens for preservation and study. These specimens were duplicates, with the originals retained in local collections. It was also during this time that the first volumes of the *Flore d'Afrique centrale* were published, initially by INEAC and later by Meise Botanic Garden, with the aim of providing descriptions and identification keys for the plant species of the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Burundi, and Rwanda. Over the years, our scientists have expanded their expertise to other important groups of organisms in tropical Africa, including fungi, unicellular algae, lichens, and myxomycetes. In response to ongoing research activities and global challenges faced by tropical African biodiversity, Meise Botanic Garden is committed to supporting local biodiversity researchers by investing in capacity-building, rehabilitating local infrastructure,

developing local field and seed bank collections, and unlocking collections and publications. To advance the monitoring of botanical diversity and to initiate and strengthen conservation efforts in the Congo Basin, we will explore the establishment of a research and training centre in Central Africa. This centre, developed in collaboration with local governmental agencies and academic institutions, would be equipped with modern research facilities and preservation capabilities, attracting both local and international scientists. It would also boost opportunities for biodiversity research funding and contribute significantly to building local expertise in the field.

Ambition 7

Doing science in state-of-the-art research infrastructure

Meise Botanic Garden is undertaking an ambitious renovation of its main collection and research building, transforming it into a state-of-the-art research campus. This project is slated for completion in 2031, which coincides with the timeline for achieving our research ambitions. While the construction period may introduce some uncertainty regarding the accessibility of the research facilities, posing potential challenges to our operations, the long-term benefits are undeniable. The new research campus, equipped with cutting-edge laboratory facilities, aligns perfectly with our scientific ambitions for the coming decade.

Priority 7.1

Relying on our science collections

Meise Botanic Garden houses an extensive and diverse array of collections, reflecting a rich history spanning more than 225 years. Today, these collections encompass over four million specimens and accessions, including living plant collections, seed bank, herbarium, molecular collections, library, archives, and art collections. In combination with our specialised staff dedicated to their technical and scientific management, they serve as a critical and unique resource for scientific research. The science collections are instrumental in advancing fundamental plant research, such as the discovery of new species and the conservation of plant diversity. They also support applied research, such as studies on crop wild relatives, help raise public awareness, and address policy-related needs by providing a comprehensive understanding of biodiversity changes in response to global change. The strategic development and management of these collections are detailed in the *Science Collections Strategy* and the *Living Collections Strategy*.

Priority 7.2

High-quality imaging for morphological and anatomical research

Comparative morphology remains the cornerstone of taxonomic research worldwide, offering invaluable insights into the structure of organisms. A variety of techniques is used to visualise structures that are not easily detected or too minute to see with the naked eye. Light microscopy stands out as the most widely used method for examining microscopic structures, and while relatively straightforward, it requires meticulous sample preparation through microtomy and staining for achieving optimal results. For the study of microalgae, fungal spores or hyphae in water samples, specialised preparation methods are employed, and stereo microscopy is used to capture detailed images of mosses and lichens. At Meise Botanic Garden, a digital Keyence microscope is commonly used when imaging leaf and seed traits, lichens, and mosses. Finally, our field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) enables the visualisation of the surfaces of the tiniest structures, such as diatoms, pollen, and spores. These imaging tools, coupled with our expertise in sample preparation and visualisation, are important assets for in-house research and collaborations with external partners. To further enhance our capabilities, we are committed to investing in cutting-edge imaging technologies. Planned upgrades include acquiring an X-ray machine for non-destructive seed viability analysis and enhancing existing equipment. Besides photographic imaging, we rely on botanical artists to make botanical drawings. These drawings provide intricate details that photographic techniques often cannot capture, making them indispensable for species descriptions and flora illustrations. The new research campus will include optimally configured spaces for photographic imaging, a dedicated studio for botanical art, and state-of-the-art laboratory facilities for advanced morphological and anatomical studies.

Priority 7.3 Expanding the molecular laboratory

The molecular lab has become an indispensable asset to our botanical, mycological, and phycological research. Molecular genetic techniques are being used for addressing a wide range of research questions, ranging from conservation and population genetics, over taxonomic research and the construction of phylogenetic hypotheses to the screening of plant pathogens and endophytes. Currently, the molecular lab is fully equipped to support most modern techniques in the field of molecular research, such as DNA barcoding, high-throughput sequencing library preparation, quality control of DNA samples, qPCR, and flow-cytometry, while sequencing is outsourced. With the lab nearing its operational capacity, the forthcoming research campus renovation will include state-of-the-art laboratory infrastructure to meet growing demands. This upgrade will feature the establishment of an ancient DNA laboratory, enabling the analysis of degraded DNA from historical and processed botanical specimens. Additionally, we aim to enhance efficiency through the automation of specific processes, such as DNA extraction, by using a pipetting robot. The integration of the current data management system in the new collection management platform Earthcape will streamline workflows and improve data handling. Furthermore, the vast datasets generated from high-throughput sequencing and genomic analyses necessitate significant computational resources. These needs are currently met by a local server for smaller tasks and by access to the Flemish Supercomputer Center for large-scale analyses. The Flemish Supercomputer Center, managed by the Research Foundation – Flanders (FWO), combines expertise in scientific computing with infrastructure across four hubs: the universities of Antwerp, Brussels, Ghent, and Leuven. It provides researchers access to facilities for computationally intensive tasks like phylogenetics and ecological modeling.

Priority 7.4 Establishing a deforestation risk commodity tracing laboratory

To determine the origin of forest risk commodities (e.g. wood, cocoa, coffee, soy), as required by the EU Deforestation Regulation, novel tracing methods are essential. This is because determining or verifying the geolocation of production and active logging areas is crucial to comply with regulations. The analytical method must be sufficiently sensitive and reliable to detect differences in samples originating from different geolocations. Meise Botanic Garden has therefore recently acquired an Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometer (ICP-OES) that can reach the required sensitivity and reliability for detecting a large range of trace elements. A microwave digestion device has been acquired for sample preparation for elemental analysis. Further investments in upgrading the forest risk commodity tracing laboratory, including for example equipment for analysis of stable isotopes, are foreseen pending demand for analyses.

Priority 7.5 Utilising our seed and pollen laboratory

Ex situ conservation of seeds and pollen requires specialised facilities that enable monitoring of viability and ensure optimal environmental conditions for storage. Our seed and pollen laboratory is equipped with cleaning and sample preparation tools designed to handle a diversity of seed samples, ranging from dust seeds to fleshy fruits. For germination studies, the laboratory houses several light- and temperature-controlled incubators that simulate optimal conditions for the germination of pollen and seeds. These incubators can be programmed to replicate cycles of temperature and light that closely resemble the natural conditions. Our newly renovated seed bank facility features a state-of-the-art configuration designed for energy and space efficiency. It includes a pre-drying room where seeds are dried under controlled conditions of 15% relative humidity and 15°C, a short-term storage room maintained at the same parameters, and a long-term storage room kept at -20°C. This setup allows us to expand our seed conservation activities while maintaining the integrity of stored samples. Looking ahead, we are exploring the installation of a cryopreservation unit. This addition would support the development of a pollen bank and provide storage options for dust seeds and tissues from recalcitrant species.

Priority 7.6 Growing plants in state-of-the-art plant cultivation facilities

Meise Botanic Garden has ample experience and facilities for conducting experiments under various conditions. Spanning 97 hectares, the domain houses multiple gardens and GIS-monitored trees, offering excellent opportunities for tracking phenology and growth in selected species. Over 25% of the domain is dedicated to natural areas. A modern glasshouse complex, the Green Ark, has recently been put into service and consists of multiple compartments with climate conditions suitable for plants from different biomes. These compartments represent four different temperature regimes, from tropical to frost-free combined with dry or humid conditions. Dedicated glasshouses are available for scientific experiments and the regeneration of scientific collections. A 10-meter-high full-ground glasshouse is specifically allocated for the regeneration and multiplication of *Musa* species. Additionally, growth and propagation chambers equipped with LED lighting and fog systems ensure optimal conditions for regenerating seedlings and clones. Plans for the new research campus include advanced temperature- and light-controlled growth chambers, alongside facilities for *in vitro* cultivation. These upgrades will support experiments requiring precise control over temperature, light, and humidity, as well as the cultivation of fungi and microalgae.

Ambition 8 Providing expert services

Meise Botanic Garden is an expert centre for the identification and use of plants, fungi, and algae. While classical identification methods traditionally rely on visual recognition, we are developing innovative approaches for more accurate and faster identification based on molecular, chemical, and AI techniques. These advanced methods, and their integration, enable us to address increasingly complex identification challenges with greater speed and precision. Our expertise extends to a range of services. For private individuals, we offer solutions such as the detection of house molds. For government agencies, we contribute to initiatives like monitoring water quality through diatom community analysis for the Flemish Environment Agency (VMM). Additionally, we provide expert guidance in tracing and regulating the illegal import of CITES-regulated plant species, as well as wood and food commodities. With the introduction of new EU legislation on deforestation-free products, we anticipate a growing demand for our expertise to support its implementation. We are also exploring the expansion of our services to include offerings such as supplying source seeds for local seed mixtures and conduction coffee quality assessments. To enhance customer satisfaction, we aim to streamline workflows and provide a clear overview of the services we offer. Tailored business cases will be developed to align our services with market demands, and where beneficial, we will collaborate with other Belgian research institutes to pool expertise. Additionally, we will intensify our promotional efforts through various channels to attract new clients and raise awareness of our capabilities.

Ambition 9 Embracing open science and open data

Open science is a cornerstone of our *science strategy* for the next decade, fostering collaboration, transparency, and accessibility across all facets of our work. As a botanic garden dedicated to understanding and preserving biodiversity, we recognise the transformative potential of open science in advancing botany and biodiversity science. By embracing open access platforms, using interoperable data repositories, and engaging in global partnerships, we aim to make our findings widely available to researchers, policymakers, and the public. Over the next ten years, our goal is to embed open science practices as a natural part of how we conduct research, fully integrated into our daily operations. To achieve this, we will conduct self-assessments of our research infrastructure, invest in robust research data management infrastructure, and provide continuous support and training to ensure research data management practices are effectively adopted and sustained. We envision a future where the taxonomic data we produce as part of our taxonomic research are rapidly made FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), enabling their seamless integration into global taxonomic infrastructures and portals (e.g. GBIF, WFO). This integration will create a cascade effect, accelerating progress in environmental and taxonomic research and ensure that communities such as citizen scientists involved in biodiversity monitoring can immediately benefit from up-to-date nomenclatural information. Realising this vision will require advancing scientific name registries, a field in which we intend to play a leading role. Through these efforts, open science will not only underpin our mission to connect people with plants but also ensure our contributions to biodiversity knowledge and conservation are impactful, widely shared, and transformative.

Ambition 10 Bringing science to the public

Priority 10.1 Training the next generation of plant scientists

As a knowledge centre for plant, fungal, and algal diversity, Meise Botanic Garden commits itself to training the next generation of plant scientists. Our educational efforts cater to a wide range of learners, from elementary school students, over internship students to MSc and PhD students. We will provide training through diverse activities, such as workshops, science fairs, internships, hosting international students, and academic supervision. Our scientists are involved in teaching master courses across most Belgian universities and serve as co-promotors and supervisors of BSc, MSc, and PhD students of all major Belgian academic institutions. To support the collaboration between Meise Botanic Garden and Flemish universities, PhD and postdoctoral fellowships are financed by us through the Research Foundation – Flanders (FWO). Over the past five years, we have observed a steady increase in applications for these grants, and we aim to further consolidate this grant system. International students and researchers from foreign partner institutes play a crucial role in our biodiversity research. We will therefore continue to invest in their training, particularly those from African countries, to strengthen local research capacities. We already train taxonomists from partner countries in Africa and Southeast Asia within the framework of the Global Taxonomy Initiative, but we intend to increase our efforts by organising workshops and courses on site.

Priority 10.2 Interacting with the public and raising awareness

Engaging the public in understanding plant diversity is a core mission of Meise Botanic Garden. We employ a variety of communication channels to share our message effectively. Displays within the domain, the gardens, and permanent exhibitions about our scientific activities are embedded within the different storylines as outlined in the *Public Outreach Strategy*. These storylines aim to educate visitors on the significance of plant diversity in everyday life, while providing insight into our research and conservation activities. A dedicated permanent exhibition showcasing our science collections and biodiversity research will be completed upon the renovation of the research campus. Social media platforms serve as vital tools for connecting with the online community. In addition to institutional updates shared through the Meise Botanic Garden accounts, individual researchers contribute by sharing their research highlights and linking back to the Garden's platforms. In addition to social media, our website remains an important window on our scientific research, expertise, and outputs. Continuous investment will ensure it remains up to date and easy to navigate. Outreach through traditional media channels will also remain an important way to communicate important findings. We actively share significant findings with the press, while our scientists lend their expertise to contextualise societal issues, as detailed in the *Public Outreach Strategy*. Finally, we remain committed to citizen science initiatives. These programs not only bring science closer to the public but also enable large-scale data collection and provide a unique platform for sharing our research activities, as emphasised in the *Science Collections Strategy*.

Priority 10.3

Publishing scientific papers and the development of online platforms

The dissemination of scientific results is essential for advancing knowledge and enabling researchers to verify hypotheses. It also plays a key role in bridging the gap between different countries by promoting equitable access to scientific knowledge and supporting societal development. Meise Botanic Garden is committed to publishing its research outcomes in an open and fair way. Beyond this commitment, the Garden actively contributes to open science at the international level through its in-house journal, *Plant Ecology and Evolution*. Published in collaboration with the Royal Botanical Society of Belgium, the journal has adopted a diamond open access model, ensuring that biodiversity data are seamlessly interlinked with relevant databases. The same applies to the journal *European Journal of Taxonomy*, in which Meise Botanic Garden is a consortium partner. The book series *Abc Taxa*, focused on taxonomic capacity building and published by a consortium including Meise Botanic Garden, the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, and the Royal Museum for Central Africa, is available through open access. We also publish *Dumortiera*, a journal about the flora and vegetation of Belgium and the adjacent areas. Besides scientific journals, Meise Botanic Garden also publishes books, floras, and reference books documenting the tropical African flora, such as the *Flore du Gabon* and the *Flore d'Afrique centrale*. These series are made openly available in PDF format as well as through online platforms. In addition to unlocking our collections on online platforms, as outlined in the *Science Collections Strategy* and the *Living Collections Strategy*, our scientists also create online resources for identification of myxomycetes, edible mushrooms, alien vascular plants, and other taxonomic groups. Future efforts will prioritise enhancing accessibility to these invaluable resources by integrating them seamlessly into online platforms and databases. This approach will ensure a synchronised user experience while facilitating connections with established international platforms for broader reach and collaboration.

Colophon

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Use of Artificial Intelligence

This text was originally written by a human author. ChatGPT was used to assist with grammar, style, and clarity improvements. The final version was reviewed and approved by a human editor to ensure accuracy and coherence.

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